

Table 2. Agronomic characters of promising rice hybrids. CLRR, Omon, Vietnam, 1993 DS.

Hybrid	Growth duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Spikelet sterility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R	105	98	15.3	74	31	26
IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	105	101	11.9	74	36	26
IR58025 A/IR532358-90-3-3 R	109	107	10.6	91	29	26
OM90-9 (check)	112	106	12.1	68	26	25

Kamini: a quality rice released in Bihar, India

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In areas of Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal, high-quality scented rice varieties are cultivated for use in specialty foods. Their price is at least 2-3 times more than that of ordinary varieties.

There are many tall, photoperiod-sensitive, high-quality scented varieties grown around the region. They have short, fine grains and excellent cooking quality. Popular variety Sugandha, released in the 1980s, has become highly susceptible to blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB). To identify high-yielding varieties to replace

Sugandha, all available land races were collected, purified, and tested in varietal trials.

One of these is Katarni, which is grown intensively in the Bhagalpur division of Bihar. SBR 80-643-14-1-1, one of the six ecotypes of Katarni, yielded more than checks and was released as Kamini.

During 5 yr of yield trials, Kamini averaged 2.9 t/ha, compared with 2.5 t/ha for check Sugandha (see table). Growers highly preferred Kamini to other varieties.

Kamini is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and tolerant of brown spot, BI, and BB. It has excellent aroma and cooking quality, especially for *palao*, a specialty rice food. It is a late aman (Jun/Jul-Dec) season variety suitable for rainfed lowland conditions of Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh. ■

Performance of SBR80-643-14-1-1 in uniform variety trials, Bihar, India, 1985-89.

Year	Entry	Yield (t/ha)				
		Sabour	Tiloundha	Patna	Pusa	Av
1985	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.4	2.6	3.0	2.1	2.6
	BR9	1.3	2.4	2.0	1.5	1.9
	Sugandha	1.5	-	3.4	2.0	2.2
	LSD	450	402	706	591	
	CV (%)	15.8	11.7	25.6	16.1	
1986	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.0	-	3.3	2.6	2.6
	BR9	1.3	-	3.3	1.9	2.1
	Sugandha	1.1	-	2.8	2.5	2.1
	LSD	323	-	350	-	
	CV (%)	13.9	-	14.5	-	
1987	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.9	-	3.4	-	3.1
	BR9	-	-	-	-	-
	Sugandha	2.6	-	2.5	-	2.5
	LSD	412	-	460	-	
	CV (%)	9.4	-	12.6	-	
1988	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.8	-	4.2	-	3.5
	BR9	1.9	-	2.6	-	2.2
	Sugandha	2.6	-	4.0	-	3.3
	LSD	470	-	380	-	
	CV (%)	11.6	-	15.6	-	
1989	SBR80-643-14-1-1	2.7	-	2.4	-	2.7
	BR9	1.9	-	-	-	1.9
	Sugandha	2.2	-	2.3	-	2.2
	LSD	354	-	218	-	
	CV (%)	10.2	-	12.1	-	

Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15: a high-quality variety in Hunan, China

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Semidwarf 86-70 (selected from IR19274-26-2-3-1-2) is a long-grained, high-quality, high-yielding variety with multiple pest resistances and wide adaptability. 86-70 was released as Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 in Hunan Province in March 1993.

The variety has an average growth duration of about 118 d. Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 performed well in 1990-91 regional trials in early rice areas. Average grain yield was 6.4 t/ha.

Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 has grain length of 7.5 mm, 3.8 L-W ratio, 1.8% average chalkiness score, high translucency, 69 mm gel consistency, alkali spreading value of 7, 19.6% average amylose content, and 9.3% protein content. Cooked grain is soft and tastes good.

Hunan soft rice is the trade name of Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15. This variety won the Golden Prize at the First Agricultural Product Exhibition of China in Oct 1992. Xiang-Zao Xian No. 15 was grown on 30,000-40,000 ha in Hunan Province in 1992 and is spreading quickly in Hubei, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, and Fujian provinces. ■

Performance of IRRI rice hybrids at Rice Research Institute (RRI), Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Pakistan

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Twenty-one hybrids using CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A were evaluated at RRI with local checks KS282 and IR6. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications conducted during 1992 kharif (monsoon) season. We transplanted 35-d-old seedlings on 15 Jul 92. Net plot size was 2 × 6.25 m² with a plant-to-plant distance of 23 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 100-50-0 kg NPK/ha. Recommended plant protection measures were adopted. We randomly selected 15

Performance of IRRI rice hybrids at RRI, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Pakistan. 1992 kharif.

Hybrid and check	Maturity duration (d)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	100-seed weight (g)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Sterile plants (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Heterosis ^a for yield over	
										KS282 (%)	IR6 (%)
IR62829 A/IR10198-66-2 R	96	362	99	28.5	156	2.04	16.0	3.10	2.1	3.7	-9.2
IR62829 A/IR15324-13-3-2 R	97	304	81	26.4	158	1.96	27.6	3.35	1.9	-9.5	-20.8
IR62829 A/IR28238-109-1-3-2-2 R	103	240	84	23.7	138	2.02	30.2	3.33	2.0	-2.3	-14.4
IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	98	326	84	26.0	189	1.92	25.3	7.23	2.5	18.9	4.1
IR62829 A/IR35366-62-1-2-2-3 R	103	333	78	25.4	160	1.87	38.7	6.37	1.8	-14.0	-24.7
IR62829 A/IR40750-82-2-2-3 R	111	346	93	27.3	233	1.88	31.3	4.13	3.1	47.9	29.5
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	96	310	77	24.4	149	2.03	24.1	4.17	2.4	14.8	0.6
IR62829 A/Pusa 150-9-3-1 R	98	256	84	26.2	155	2.09	32.3	5.31	2.0	-2.1	-14.3
IR58025 A/IR10198-66-2 R	108	230	103	27.6	160	2.56	21.0	2.00	3.3	61.0	41.0**
IR58025 A/IR15324-13-3-2 R	96	208	101	29.0	185	2.38	23.4	3.11	2.2	5.3*	-7.8
IR58025 A/IR20933-68-21-1-2-1 R	111	234	108	29.3	161	1.92	21.1	0.00	2.1	3.9	-9.0
IR58025 A/IR21567-18-3 R	108	243	99	25.6	129	2.74	37.6	5.33	2.1	2.2	-10.5
IR62829 A/IR28238-109-1-3-2-2 R	104	246	101	27.8	170	1.89	39.6	8.15	2.7	32.4	16.0
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	108	234	103	25.6	115	2.03	28.6	0.00	2.8	36.1	19.2
IR58025 A/IR32419-28-3-1-3 R	103	211	102	29.0	203	2.17	33.0	6.55	1.8	-11.8	-22.8
IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-2-3 R	104	202	95	27.5	199	2.33	31.1	5.98	1.7	-16.8	-27.1
IR58025 A/IR39323-182-2-3-3 R	103	195	93	30.3	234	2.38	33.4	7.10	2.6	24.3	8.9
IR58025 A/IR40750-82-2-2-3 R	119	274	94	23.9	152	2.12	23.5	2.30	3.6	74.8	53.0**
IR58025 A/IR66 R	105	272	106	24.3	144	2.30	26.5	2.71	2.3	13.1	-1.0
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	98	202	96	28.1	155	2.04	18.9	4.11	2.2	4.0*	-8.9
IR58025 A/Pusa 150-9-3-1 R	93	240	101	27.6	148	2.34	31.4	3.13	3.0	47.1	28.8
KS282	103	333	99	25.2	145	2.76	20.1	0.00	2.1		
IR6		104	400	102	27.4	161	2.75	12.6	0.00	2.4	
LSD (0.05)								1.1			
CV (%)								7.4			

* = better than low-yielding check KS282. ** = better than high-yielding check IR6.

plants/genotype per replication to measure plant height, panicle length, and spikelets/panicle. We used 100 seeds from the different randomly selected plants in each replication to measure 100-seed weight. Panicles/m² per replication were counted. To determine maturity, duration days were counted from the date of transplanting to the stage of physiological maturity when about 90% of the grains were mature. Percent sterile plants per plot were counted and yield at 14% moisture level was recorded in t/ha.

Panicles/m² ranged from 195 to 400, plant height from 77 to 103 cm, and panicle length from 23.7 to 30.3 cm. Spikelets/panicle ranged from 115 to 234 and 100-seed weight from 1.87 to

2.76 g. Maximum spikelet sterility was observed in IR62829 A/IR35366-62-1-2-2-3R. Only hybrids IR58025 A/IR40750-82-2-2-3R and IR58025 A/IR10198-66-2R significantly outperformed all other hybrids and checks. The IR58025 A combinations, however, significantly outperformed IR62829 A hybrids and checks for most traits.

Of the 21 IRRI hybrids, eight performed significantly better than high-yielding check IR6 and three performed significantly better than KS282 (see table). IR6 had more panicles/m² and heavier 100-seed weight than other hybrid combinations. IR58025 A/Pusa150-9-3-1R matured in 93 d, IR62829 A/IR40750-82-2-2-3R in 111 d, and IR58025A/IR40750-82-2-2-

3R in 119 d. These hybrid combinations showed 47.1, 47.9, and 74.8% more standard heterosis over KS282, and 28.8, 29.5, and 53.1% over IR6, respectively. Cross IR62829 A/IR40750-2-2-3R showed 3.8, 8.4, and 61.2% more standard heterosis over KS282 for panicles/m², panicle length, and spikelets/panicle, respectively.

Severe attacks of leafhopper and whitebacked planthopper, partial spikelet sterility (50-75% fertile spikelets for most genotypes), incomplete panicle exertion, late transplanting of seedlings, and water stress at flowering caused low yields of hybrids and checks. ■